

SOCIAL-PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF ENSURING THE SAFETY OF LIFE OF CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL EDUCATIONAL NEEDS IN CONTINUOUS INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Kobilova Shakhnoza Khudaishukurovna

Associate professor (PhD) of the department of Special Pedagogy,
faculty of Pedagogy, Chirchik state pedagogical university

kabilovashaxnoza4@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14263828>

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada alohida ta'limga ehtiyoji bo'lgan bolalarni hayot xavfsizligini ta'minlashning ijtimoiy pedagogik jihatlarini ilmiy nuqtai nazardan yoritilgan bo'lib, ta'lim jarayoni bilan bevosita bog'liq bo'lgan texnogen xususiyatli favqulodda vaziyatlar, tabiat hodisalariga munosib yondashish, informatsion g'oya va targ'ibotlarga qarshi kurash kontekstida o'quvchilarni favqulodda vaziyatlarning salbiy ta'siridan himoya qilish masalalarini psixologik-pedagogik jihatdan o'rganilgan hamda ilmiy mulohazalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Alohida ta'limga ehtiyoji bo'lgan bolalar, ruhiy va jismoniy, kognitiv faoliyat kamchiliklari, hayot xavfsizligi, uzluksiz inklyuziv ta'lim jarayoni, motivatsion omillar, o'quv jarayoni, tayyorgarlik darajasi va kasbiy rivojlanish qobiliyatlari, pedagogik-psixologik mexanizm, integratsiya, xavfsiz xatti-harakat.

Аннотация: В данной статье социально-педагогические аспекты обеспечения безопасности детей с особыми образовательными потребностями освещены с научной точки зрения, а образовательный процесс напрямую связан с чрезвычайными ситуациями техногенного характера, соответствующим подходом к природным явлениям, информативные идеи и рекламные акции. в контексте борьбы с ним изучены психолого-педагогические и научные заключения по вопросам защиты студентов от негативного воздействия чрезвычайных ситуаций.

Ключевые слова: Дети с особыми образовательными потребностями, психическое и физическое, дефицит познавательной активности, безопасность жизнедеятельности, непрерывный инклюзивный образовательный процесс, мотивационные факторы, образовательный процесс, уровень подготовки и профессионального развития навыков, педагогико-психологический механизм, интеграция, безопасное поведение.

Annotation: In this article, the socio-pedagogical aspects of ensuring the safety of children with special educational needs are covered from a scientific point of view, protecting students from the negative effects of emergencies in the context of man-made emergency situations that are directly related to the educational process, appropriate approach to natural phenomena, informative ideas and propaganda. psychological-pedagogical issues were studied and scientific opinions were given.

Key words: Children with special educational needs, mental and physical, cognitive activity deficits, life safety, continuous inclusive educational process, motivational factors, educational process, level of training and professional development skills, pedagogical-psychological mechanism, integration, safe behavior.

In every society where the human factor is glorified, the mechanism of social protection rises to the level of state policy and all factors of its implementation are aligned with the principles of humanism. Organization of the practical activities of children with mental and physical special educational needs is one of the important issues, and creating an effective educational environment in the process of professional training and personal development (taking into account age, gender and individual characteristics) to form their readiness for a safe life remains one of the demands of the time.

From this point of view, it is necessary to scientifically research the factors and sources of children with special educational needs to increase their motivation for practical activities, to encourage them, to develop their skills and abilities, to alleviate the deficiencies of cognitive activity, and to form individual typological characteristics.

Creating a healthy continuous educational environment for children with special educational needs, developing the appropriate knowledge, skills and qualifications to prepare them for certain fields and professions is an important social necessity in shaping their readiness for a safe life.

The educational and rehabilitation environment of continuous inclusive education in our society is organizationally, methodologically and technologically adapted to the specific needs of children with special educational needs, and creates conditions for developing vocational education programs, protecting their health, and implementing independent activities. The goal of this program is to further strengthen the information and socio-cultural space of a continuous inclusive educational institution.

This environment is the basis for full or partial compensation (compensation) of the limitations of the vital activity of children with special educational needs, allowing them to act as competitive specialists in the labor market.

In the vocational training of children with special educational needs, it is advisable to implement the educational process on the basis of:

- creating conditions for the development of the potential abilities of the individual (taking into account the general laws of the development of the personality of children with special educational needs with impaired physical and mental abilities and specific features);
- forming a barrier-free learning environment (differentiated and individually oriented approaches to children with special educational needs);
- ensuring the health of children with special educational needs;
- creating conditions for the theoretical and practical training of future specialists in the field of therapeutic physical education in combination with therapeutic and recreational activities and therapeutic exercises (medical, physical and psychological training);
- developing optimal methods of assisting in the development of professional rehabilitation of children with special educational needs;
- ensuring self-employment of children with special educational needs in a socialized environment (in classrooms, limiting isolated employment);
- special design of classrooms for children with special educational needs, creation of sanitary and hygienic conditions, organization of treatment and rehabilitation work;
- psychological assistance for children with special educational needs, socio-legal consultations, practical assistance in finding a job, solving social, household and socio-cultural issues related to the process of continuous education;

- strengthening pedagogical and psychological work on adapting children with special educational needs to social life and labor activity, as well as self-realization.

The orientation of children with special educational needs to practical activities requires the creation of a specialized material and technical base, including training classes in professional disciplines for visually impaired students and classrooms well-equipped with demonstration tools (models, raised tablets and tables), stands, technical equipment. Devices for connecting to social networks must also be adapted to the characteristics of their disease (personal computers, voice recorders, CD players). Also, all sources of professional and interdisciplinary cycles for each child with special educational needs should be provided with specially individualized electronic publications. It is very important that the library fund of the educational institution is provided with basic and additional educational literature for all stages, as well as official, reference and bibliographic and periodical publications. This creates the opportunity for children with special educational needs to quickly exchange information with local, regional and regional continuing education institutions.

The educational process aimed at solving the problems of continuous inclusive education is distinguished by the degree of goal-setting, which is aimed at implementing important issues related to the age characteristics of children with special educational needs, their level of preparation and professional development capabilities.

It should be emphasized that today, in order to effectively implement the continuous inclusive education system in our society and form the professional skills of children with special educational needs, it is advisable to teach the main and special parts of the educational cycles based on modern, state and social needs, as well as the requirements of the market economy.

We believe that it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

history (it should be supplemented with the life and work of historical figures who provide internal motivation and educate the will of man); the foundations of spirituality (understanding human dignity as the highest value and aligning it with factors directed towards the conscious activity of forming oneself as a person); psychology (enriched with human will, its inherent qualities, the foundations of conscious activity, motivational training and practical exercises); physical culture (replenished with sources of conscious education and stimulation of the human body); life safety (replenished with socio-pedagogical and psychological factors of human self-preservation); information security (aimed at blocking negative sources of information attacks and threats, as well as the psychological impact on consciousness and activity).

Also, the following issues are considered priority in organizing the practical processes of children with special educational needs:

- firstly, training and production should be aimed at the full formation of professional skills and qualifications of children with special educational needs, and should be carried out in school laboratories and production organizations equipped with specially individualized modern innovative technological equipment for mastering practical competencies;

- secondly, the formation of professional skills and improvement of practical competencies of children with special educational needs should be carried out on the basis of a coordinated program developed with the educational institution and partner organizations;

- thirdly, the practical process should be carried out without affecting the health and mental state of children with special educational needs, taking into account physical fatigue,

and based on the essence of the concept of unhindered movement from the point of view of "convenient time" and "convenient place";

-fourthly, children with special educational needs should be directed to activities that strengthen their health and provide professional motivation, based on their desires and wishes, as well as interests and abilities;

-fifthly, the organization of internships for children with special educational needs is provided with a program and conditions that allow them to evaluate their qualifications, knowledge, practical experience and acquired professional competencies;

-sixthly, the formation of the competence of perseverance, critical self-evaluation and self-control, as a necessary component of the internship process for children with special educational needs, as well as the correct assessment of their successes and shortcomings in their activities;

-seventhly, the full implementation of programs aimed at ensuring the socialization process of children with special educational needs with others during the internship process, and the formation of a healthy socio-psychological environment for the formation of adequate behavior in the team.

It is necessary to develop a methodology for the formation of life safety competence of children with special educational needs in practice-oriented activities.

The integration and implementation of the pedagogical and psychological potential of general professional disciplines, which allows updating and enriching the knowledge and skills of children with special educational needs, their individual capabilities in the field of life safety, helps to develop a holistic perception of life activity. Also, self-preservation and the environment as a recognized type of activity are formed, their integration with society is formed, and the process of social adaptation is transferred to a recognized type of activity.

From this point of view, it is necessary to develop the subject "Life Safety" in accordance with the knowledge, skills and qualifications of children with special educational needs in terms of their life direction and type of activity, and to develop the safety features of professional and social adaptation.

It is also advisable to pay attention to the following as pedagogically implemented tasks in the formation of children with special educational needs for a safe life: determining pre-existing (basic) knowledge in the field of life safety; identifying structural and functional systems of environmental perception in children with special educational needs, and analyzing their changes; determining the role of the field of professional knowledge in managing and organizing the life safety of children with special educational needs; developing certain methods of protecting children with special educational needs from negative factors in the life process, and promoting their social adaptation in society; developing the concept of safe behavior in the personality of children with special educational needs; forming the readiness of children with special educational needs for a safe life based on pedagogical and psychological factors; saturating children with special educational needs with a source of knowledge that prioritizes issues of personal safety and health.

A person undergoes formation processes at different stages of ontogenesis. The use of a differentiated approach in the educational process, taking into account the age and individual characteristics of children with special educational needs, allows us to compensate for or correct the identified shortcomings in the development of the individual.

We believe that it is appropriate to base this scientific hypothesis on the ideas of B.K. TuPONOGOV. According to his point of view, differentiated training improves the processes of perception, thinking, memory, speech activation, completeness of reproductive activity, adequacy of concepts, and knowledge of the surrounding world in students with disabilities[7].

In conclusion, based on the above considerations, it is important to prioritize practical activities in order to fully align the goals and objectives of continuous inclusive education, developing the motivation of students to live a safe life in an environment of continuous inclusive education, creating a healthy lifestyle for children with special needs and becoming the most active members of society, while putting forward the scientific hypothesis that the integration of special subjects taught to children with special needs with vocational subjects is a necessary condition for their social adaptation.

References:

- 1.Ermakov, V.P. Professional orientation uchashchikhsya s narusheni-yami zreniya: Medicine, psychology, pedagogy: Posobie dlya uchitelya / Pod ed. V.I. Seliverstova. - M.: Humanist. izd. Center "VLADOS", 2002. - 176 p.
- 2.Kobilova Sh.Kh. Compatibility of psychological-pedagogical activity in inclusive education and its prospects // European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. Nov. 2022, Vol. 9, 40–46.
- 3.Kobilova Sh.Kh. Organization of pedagogical activity and psychological coordination in continuous inclusive education / New Uzbekistan; Collection of materials of the Republican scientific and technical conference on science, education and innovation (April 9-10, 2024)- Jizzakh -2024. -B.122-126
- 4.TuPONOGOV, B.K. Organization of the correctional-pedagogical process in the school for blind and weak-sighted children / B.K. TuPONOGOV: methodical-skoe posobie dlya pedagogov i rukoviteley special (corrective) educational resource. - M.: Humanitarian izd. center "VLADOS", 2011. - 223 p
- 5.Eshnaev N.J. Scientific and theoretical analysis of factors shaping the professional mobility of future pedagogical specialists / Teacher and Continuing Education 3/2-issue 2023 -P.102-108
- 6.Eshnaev N.J. In Social pedagogical and psychological factors of training a modern mobile specialist / Vocational education. Scientific-methodological, practical, educational journal. 2023, issue 3. -P.221-225
- 7.Mirzarakhimova.G.I. DYNAMICS OF INTELLIGENCE OF LOW-SPEECH IN ADOLESCENTS // SCIENCE AND INNOVATION. - 2023. - T. 2. - № 3. - С. 84-87. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7707440>
- 8.Ozodqulov, O. . (2024). VATANPARVARLIK RUHINI TALABALARDA RIVOJLANTIRISH PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. Центральноеазиатский журнал академических исследований, 2(10 Part 2), 37–41. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/cajar/article/view/38469>
- 9.Xusanova, N. . (2024). FACTORS INFLUENCING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN WITH DIFFERENT TEMPERAMENTS. Евразийский журнал

социальных наук, философии и культуры, 4(10), 17–20. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejsspc/article/view/37667>

10. Amangeldiyev, S. . (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL ACTIVITY IN OLD AGE: A KEY FACTOR FOR PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING. Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры, 4(10), 12–16. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejsspc/article/view/37666>

11. Abduqodirova D., Pardaboyeva M. THE ROLE OF EMOTIONAL CREATIVITY IN STUDENTS' DECISION-MAKING // INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF NATURAL AND SOCIAL-HUMANITARIAN SCIENCES. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 7. – С. 27-30.

12. Jo'rayev, S. ., & Abdurasulov, J. (2024). SUBJECT, TASKS AND CONTENT OF STUDYING THE BASICS OF MILITARY-PATRIOTIC EDUCATION. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(7), 149–153. извлечено от <https://www.econferences.ru/index.php/arims/article/view/13106>

13. Абдурасулов, Ж. (2022). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В УСВОЕНИИ УРОКОВ ИСТОРИИ. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON LEARNING AND TEACHING, 1(10), 113–115. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php/ict/article/view/1778>